

CyberSecDome

An innovative Virtual Reality based intrusion detection, incident investigation and response approach for enhancing the resilience, security, privacy and accountability of complex and heterogeneous digital systems and infrastructures.

CyberSecDome Open Call

Proposals Submission Guideline

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1 Introduction

This guideline provides practical instructions to assist applicants in preparing and submitting their proposals for the CyberSecDome Open Call. It complements the CyberSecDome Open Call General Guide, the CyberSecDome Open Call Round 1 General Guide, and the Proposal Template, ensuring a smooth submission process.

2 Documents to Review Before Submission

Applicants are strongly encouraged to read the following documents thoroughly:

1. [CyberSecDome Open Call General Guide](#) outlines eligibility, evaluation criteria, and key requirements.
2. [CyberSecDome Round 1 Guide](#): This focuses on the specific objectives, topics, and expected outcomes of Round 1.
3. [CyberSecDome Proposal Template](#): This provides the structure and formatting requirements for the proposal.
4. [CyberSecDome Third-Party Funding Agreement \(TPFA\)](#): This outlines the terms and conditions of funding and collaboration.

All documents are available for download on the CyberSecDome website (<https://cybersecdome.eu>) or upon request via info@cybersecdome.eu or opencall@cybersecdome.eu

3 Support and Assistance

- For queries or assistance during the application process:
 - Email: Reach out to opencall@cybersecdome.eu or info@cybersecdome.eu
 - Social Media: Updates and announcements are shared on:
 - LinkedIn: CyberSecDome LinkedIn
 - X (Twitter): @CyberSecDome_EU
 - YouTube: CyberSecDome Channel
- Submission Platform: Contact F6S support for technical issues and/or opencall@cybersecdome.eu regarding any difficulties you may face on the submission platform.

4 Steps for Proposal Submission

1. Registration on F6S Platform:
 - Access the CyberSecDome Open Call Round 1 submission page at <https://www.f6s.com/cybersecdome-open-call-round-1>.

- Applicants with existing F6S accounts can log in directly, simplifying the process. Registration on F6S is not mandatory but is recommended for updates on the proposal status.
2. Proposal Preparation:
 - Use the Proposal Template provided. Ensure all sections are completed, and supporting documentation (e.g., budget breakdowns, CVs, and letters of commitment) is included.
 - Adhere to the formatting and length requirements outlined in the Proposal Template.
 3. Proposal Submission:
 - Upload the completed proposal and additional documents (if required) on the F6S platform.
 - Select the relevant topic(s) addressed by your proposal.
 - Double-check that all mandatory fields and documents are completed.
 4. Submission Confirmation:
 - Once submitted, applicants will receive an email confirmation with a unique reference number.
 - Use this reference number for any correspondence regarding your application.

5 Key Tips for Successful Submission

- **Start Early:** Begin preparing your proposal well before the submission deadline to allow time for clarifications or adjustments.
- **Read All Materials:** Ensure you understand the scope, objectives, and evaluation criteria of the Open Call.
- **Ask for Help:** Contact the CyberSecDome team for assistance with unclear sections or technical difficulties.
- **Review Thoroughly:** Ensure compliance with all submission requirements and verify that documents are free of errors.